

Synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of imidazole derivatives of some non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs

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Manuscript received 2 August 2006, revised 5 October 2007, accepted 26 November 2007

Abstract : A series of imidazole derivatives of NSAIDs (4a-l) have been prepared by condensation of NSAIDs hydrazides (1,2) with substituted oxazolones and evaluated for anti-inflammatory and gastrointestinal toxicity, which showed good anti-inflammatory activity and reduced gastrointestinal toxicity as compared to parent drug.

Keywords : Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, carragenin, oxazolone, imidazole.

Introduction

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are used for the treatment of arthritis and all types of pains and trauma. They are contraindicated in gastrointestinal disturbances and their prolonged use leads to gastrointestinal ulceration, bleeding and nephrotoxicity¹, due to the presence of free carboxylic group in the structure. The use of prodrugs to temporarily mask the acidic group of NSAIDs has been postulated as an approach to decrease the gastrointestinal toxicity due to the direct contact effect². Thus in the present study, the carboxylic acid group of naproxen, ketoprofen and ibuprofen were temporarily masked by converting them to substituted imidazole derivatives to impart good anti-inflammatory activity³ and reduced gastrointestinal toxicity.

Results and discussion

Substituted oxazolones (4a-l) were prepared by condensation of benzoylglycine with substituted aldehydes using synthetic method outlined in the scheme⁴. These oxazolones were transformed into imidazole by condensation of alkanolic acid hydrazides (3) via their esters in pyridine⁴.

All the compounds prepared were adequately characterized by their elemental analysis, spectral (IR, NMR) data.

The compounds were screened for their anti-inflammatory activity by hind paw method⁵. The standard drugs naproxen, ketoprofen and ibuprofen (50 mg/kg body

weight) and test drug (50 mg/kg body weight) were used. The results were quite impressive. In ketoprofen series all the compounds (4e-h) where COOH group is replaced by substituted imidazoles showed percentage inhibition (53, 53, 60, 50) much higher than the parent drug (33.33). Also in ibuprofen series all the compounds (6i-l) were found to show percentage inhibition (43.33, 53, 46.66, 50) much higher than the parent drug (40) while in naproxen series compound (6a,c,d) showed % inhibition (56.66, 66.66, 60) comparable to naproxen (73) and (6b) showed inhibition much less than (40%) the parent drug. The compounds were also screened for ulcerogenic activity by reported method⁶. The mean number of ulcers formed in gastric mucosa were counted. Drug derivatives (6a-l) showed number of ulcers, 2.50, 2.48, 2.70, 2.56, 2.59, 2.46, 2.72, 2.00, 2.56, 2.49, 2.90 and 2.65 respectively (standard 3.90, 4.60, 4.20). Thus replacing COOH group of NSAIDs by substituted imidazoles not only increased percentage inhibition of swelling but were also less irritatory to gastric mucosa. On the whole, all the compounds have better anti-inflammatory and ulcerogenic activity as compared to standard drugs.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded in open capillary tubes on electrically heating block and are uncorrected. The purity of compounds were monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) using silica gel-G as stationary phase and chloroform : methanol (95 : 5) and petroleum ether : ethyl acetate (80 : 20) were used as solvent systems.

Scheme of reactions :

Solvents like methanol and ethanol were purified in laboratory.

Table 1. Effect of compounds synthesized on carragenin induced paw edema in rats

Sl. no.	Compd. (% inhibition)	No. of animals used	Average body wt. (g)	Dose (mg/k)	Mean paw swelling (\pm S.D.)
1.	Control	5	234	NaCMC	0.3
2.	Naproxen (73)	5	218	50	0.08 (\pm 0.0171)
3.	6a (56.66)	5	220	50	0.13 (\pm 0.0037)
4.	6b (40)	5	218	50	0.18 (\pm 0.0096)
5.	6c (66.66)	5	210	50	0.10 (\pm 0.0117)
6.	6d (60)	5	238	50	0.12 (\pm 0.0064)
7.	Ketoprofen (33.33)	5	230	50	0.20 (\pm 0.0149)
8.	6e (53)	5	232	50	0.14 (\pm 0.0010)
9.	6f (53)	5	235	50	0.14 (\pm 0.0010)
10.	6g (60)	5	206	50	0.12 (\pm 0.0064)
11.	6h (50)	5	240	50	0.15 (\pm 0.0015)
12.	Ibuprofen (40)	5	226	50	0.18 (\pm 0.0096)
13.	6i (43.33)	5	232	50	0.17 (\pm 0.0069)
14.	6j (53)	5	228	50	0.14 (\pm 0.0010)
15.	6k (46.66)	5	228	50	0.16 (\pm 0.0042)
16.	6l (50)	5	236	50	0.15 (\pm 0.0015)

Synthesis of esters (2) :

To acid (NSAIDs) (1) (0.1449 mol) in dry methanol was added 2.85 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid refluxed for 6 h under anhydrous conditions. Reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of reaction excess of alcohol was distilled off and allowed to cool. The residue was extracted with carbon tetrachloride, washed with a strong solution of sodium hydrogen carbonate followed by distilled water, dried on anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and collected pure ester of corresponding acids.

Synthesis of hydrazide (3) :

Equimolar quantity (0.0527 mol) of ester and hydrazine was taken in sufficient amount of absolute alcohol and refluxed it for 6 h. After completion of reaction excess amount of alcohol was distilled off and hot solution was poured on crushed ice. White crystals of hydrazide were collected, dried and recrystallized with ethyl alcohol.

Synthesis of oxazolone (5) :

A mixture of hippuric acid (acetyl glycine) (4) (0.10 mol), aldehyde (0.15 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.075 mol) and acetic anhydride (0.25 mol) was heated on a sand bath with constant shaking till the mixture liquified completely. The liquid was cooled and left overnight.

The solid which separated out was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallised from carbon tetrachloride to give crystalline solid oxazolone.

Synthesis of substituted imidazole derivatives of NSAIDs (6a-l) :

N-[2-Aryl-(4-phenylethylene)-5-oxo-4,5-dihydroimidazole]-6'-methoxy-2'-naphthyl- α -methyl acetamide (6a) :

Equimolar concentration (0.1 mol) of hydrazide (2a) and oxazolone (5a) were refluxed in pyridine (25 ml) for 4 to 6 h. The resulting mixture was poured on crushed ice containing HCl (1 to 2 ml). The solid thus separated was recrystallized from ethanol. Molecular formula ($C_{30}H_{25}N_3O_3$), mol. wt. (475), m.p. 128 °C, yield 60%; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH stretch), 1750 (cyclic -CO-N), 1635 (CONH), 1608, 1513 (C=N, C=C); 1H NMR $CDCl_3$: δ 8.25 (1H, br hump, NH), 7.56 (6H, m, ArH), 7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 7.36 (5H, m, ArH), 6.48 (brs, =CH), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.52 (1H, q, J 2 Hz, CH_3CH), 1.46 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, $CH(CH_3)-CONH$).

All other compounds (6b to 7) were prepared by the same procedure.

N-[2-Aryl-(4-*p*-chlorophenylethylene)-5-oxo-4,5-dihydroimidazole]-6'-methoxy-2'-naphthyl- α -methyl acetamide (6b) :

Molecular formula ($C_{30}H_{24}N_3O_3Cl$), mol. wt. (509.5), m.p. 132 °C, yield 42%; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH ali), 1750 (cyclic -CO-N), 1635 (CONH), 1608, 1513 (C=N, C=C); 1H NMR $CDCl_3$: δ 8.25 (1H, br hump, NH), 7.78 (2H, m, Ar 3',5'), 7.66 (2H, m, Ar 2',6'), 7.56 (6H, m, ArH), 7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 6.48 (brs, =CH), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.52 (1H, q, J 2 Hz, CH_3CH), 1.46 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, $-CH(CH_3)-CONH$).

N-[2-Aryl-(4-*o*-nitrophenylethylene)-5-oxo-4,5-dihydroimidazole]-6'-methoxy-2'-naphthyl- α -methyl acetamide (6c) :

Molecular formula ($C_{30}H_{24}N_4O_5$), mol. wt. (520), m.p. 138 °C, yield 55%; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH stretch), 1750 (cyclic -CO-N), 1635 (CONH), 1608, 1513 (C=N, C=C); 1H NMR $CDCl_3$: δ 8.25 (1H, br hump, NH), 7.92 (1H, d, J 6.2 Hz, Ar 6'), 7.86 (3H, m, Ar 3',4',5'), 7.56 (5H, m, ArH), 7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 6.48 (brs, CH_2), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.52 (1H, q, J 4 Hz, CH_3CH) and 1.46 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, $CH(CH_3)-CONH$).

N-[2-Aryl-(4-*p*-nitrophenylethylene)-5-oxo-4,5-dihydroimidazole]-6'-methoxy-2'-naphthyl- α -methyl acetamide (6d) :

Molecular formula ($C_{30}H_{24}N_4O_5$), mol. wt. (520), m.p. 142 °C, yield 64%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH stretch), 1750 (cyclic -CO-N), 1635 (CONH), 1608, 1513 (C=N, C=C); 1H NMR $CDCl_3$: δ 8.25 (1H, brs, NH), 7.96 (2H, m, Ar 3',5'), 7.92 (2H, m, Ar 2',6'), 7.56 (6H, m, ArH), 7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 6.48 (br s, =CH), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.52 (1H, q, CH_3CH), 1.46 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, $CH(CH_3)-CONH$).

N-[2-Aryl-(4-phenylethylene)-5-oxo-4,5-dihydroimidazole]- α -benzophenone- α -methyl acetamide (**6e**):

Molecular formula ($C_{32}H_{25}N_3O_3$), mol. wt. (499), m.p. 96 °C, yield 53%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH stretch), 1750 (cyclic -CO-N), 1635 (CONH), 1608, 1513 (C=N, C=C); 1H NMR $CDCl_3$: δ 12.32 (1H, NH, D_2O), 7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 7.36 (5H, m, ArH), 7.25 (9H, m, ArH), 6.40 (br s, =CH- C_6H_5), 4.55 (1H, q, J 7 Hz, $CHCH_3$), 1.75 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, $CO-CH_3$).

N-[2-Aryl-(4-*p*-chlorophenylethylene)-5-oxo-4,5-dihydroimidazole]- α -benzophenone- α -methyl acetamide (**6f**):

Molecular formula ($C_{32}H_{24}N_3O_3Cl$), mol. wt. (533.5), m.p. 96 °C, yield 56%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH stretch), 1750 (cyclic -CO-N), 1635 (CONH), 1608, 1513 (C=N, C=C); 1H NMR $CDCl_3$: δ 12.32 (1H, s, NH, D_2O), 7.78 (2H, m, Ar 3',5'), 7.66 (2H, m, Ar 2',6'), 7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 7.25 (8H, m, ArH), 6.40 (brs, =CH- C_6H_5), 4.55 (1H, q, J 7 Hz, $CHCH_3$), 1.75 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, $CH-CH_3$).

N-[2-Aryl-(4-*o*-nitrophenylethylene)-5-oxo-4,5-dihydroimidazole]- α -benzophenone- α -methyl acetamide (**6g**):

Molecular formula ($C_{32}H_{24}N_4O_5$), mol. wt. (544), m.p. 90 °C, yield 44%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH stretch), 1750 (cyclic -CO-N), 1635 (CONH), 1608, 1513 (C=N, C=C); 1H NMR $CDCl_3$: δ 12.32 (1H, s, NH, D_2O), 7.96 (3H, m, ArH 3',4',5'), 7.92 (1H, d, J 6.2 Hz, Ar 6'), 7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 7.25 (9H, m, ArH), 6.40 (brs, =CH- C_6H_5), 4.55 (1H, q, J 7 Hz, $CHCH_3$) and 1.75 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, $CO-CH_3$).

N-[2-Aryl-(4-*p*-nitrophenylethylene)-5-oxo-4,5-dihydroimidazole]- α -benzophenone- α -methyl acetamide (**6h**):

Molecular formula ($C_{32}H_{24}N_4O_5$), mol. wt. (544), m.p. 92 °C, yield 58%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH ali), 1750 (cyclic -CO-N), 1635 (CONH), 1608, 1513 (C=N, C=C); 1H NMR $CDCl_3$: δ 12.32 (1H, s, NH, D_2O),

7.96 (2H, m, Ar 3',5'), 7.92 (2H, m, Ar 2',6'), 7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 7.25 (9H, m, ArH), 6.40 (brs, =CH- C_6H_5), 4.55 (1H, q, J 7 Hz, $CHCH_3$) and 1.75 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, $CO-CH_3$).

N-[2-Aryl-(4-phenylethylene)-5-oxo-4,5-dihydroimidazole]- α -isobutylphenylmethyl acetamide (**6i**):

Molecular formula ($C_{29}H_{29}N_3O$), mol. wt. (461), m.p. 141 °C, yield 56%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH stretch), 1750 (cyclic -CO-N), 1635 (CONH), 1608, 1513 (C=N, C=C); 1H NMR $CDCl_3$: δ 8.25 (1H, brs, NH), 7.56 (5H, m, ArH), 7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 7.30 (4H, m, ArH), 6.48 (1H, brs, = CH_2), 3.70 (1H, q, CH_3CH), 2.38 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, CH_2 Ar), 1.78 (1H, m, $(CH_3)_2CH$), 1.49 (3H, d, J 8 Hz, CH_3-CH) and 0.89 (6H, d, J 6 Hz, $(CH_3)_2CH$).

N-[2-Aryl-(4-chlorophenylethylene)-5-oxo-4,5-dihydroimidazole]-4-isobutylphenyl- α -methyl acetamide (**6j**):

Molecular formula ($C_{29}H_{28}N_4O_5Cl$), mol. wt. (495.5), m.p. 128 °C, yield 68%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH ali), 1750 (cyclic -CO-N), 1635 (CONH), 1608, 1513 (C=N, C=C); 1H NMR $CDCl_3$: δ 8.25 (1H, brs, NH), 7.86 (2H, m, ArH 3',5'), 7.60 (2H, m, ArH 2',6'), 7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 7.30 (4H, m, ArH), 6.48 (1H, brs, = CH_2), 3.70 (1H, q, CH_3-CH), 2.38 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, CH_2 Ar), 1.78 (1H, m, $(CH_3)_2CH$), 1.49 (3H, d, J 8 Hz, CH_3CH) and 0.89 (6H, d, J 6 Hz, $(CH_3)_2CH$).

N-[2-Aryl-(4-*o*-nitrophenylethylene)-5-oxo-4,5-dihydroimidazole]-4-isobutyl phenyl- α -methyl acetamide (**6k**):

Molecular formula ($C_{29}H_{28}N_4O_5$), mol. wt. (506), m.p. 126 °C, yield 65%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH ali), 1750 (cyclic -CO-N), 1635 (CONH), 1608, 1513 (C=N, C=C); 1H NMR $CDCl_3$: δ 8.25 (1H, br, NH), 7.96 (3H, m, Ar 3',4',5'), 7.92 (1H, d, J 6.2 Hz, Ar 6'), 7.56 (5H, m, ArH), 7.30 (4H, m, ArH), 6.48 (2H, brs, = CH_2), 3.70 (1H, q, CH_3CH), 2.38 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, CH_2 Ar), 1.78 (1H, m, $(CH_3)_2CH$), 1.49 (3H, d, J 8 Hz, CH_3CH) and 0.89 (6H, d, J 6 Hz, $(CH_3)_2CH$).

N-[2-Aryl-(4-*o*-nitrophenylethylene)-5-oxo-4,5-dihydroimidazole]-4-isobutyl phenyl- α -methyl acetamide (**6l**):

Molecular formula ($C_{29}H_{28}N_4O_5$), mol. wt. (506), m.p. 140 °C, yield 52%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH stretch), 1750 (cyclic -CO-N), 1635 (CONH), 1608, 1513 (C=N, C=C); 1H NMR $CDCl_3$: δ 8.25 (1H, brss, NH), 7.96 (2H, m, Ar 3',5'), 7.92 (2H, m, Ar 2',6'), 7.50 (5H, m, ArH), 7.30 (4H, m, ArH), 6.48 (2H, brs, = CH_2), 3.70

(1H, q, CH₃CH), 2.38 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz, CH₂Ar), 1.78 (1H, m, (CH₃)₂CH), 1.49 (3H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH₃CH), 0.89 (6H, d, *J* 6 Hz, (CH₃)₂CH).

Pharmacological studies :

The compounds prepared were screened for their antiinflammatory activity and gastrointestinal toxicity.

Antiinflammatory activity : The imidazole activity of NSAIDs (ibuprofen, naproxen and ketoprofen) were screened for their antiinflammatory activity by hind-paw method⁵. Carragenin an irritant was injected subcutaneously into the hind paw of the albino rats at a concentration of 1 mg/ml to produce edema. The standard drugs naproxen, ketoprofen and ibuprofen and the test drugs at dose level 50 mg/kg body weight were administered orally.

Gastrointestinal toxicity : The compounds were screened for ulcerogenic activity by reported method⁶. Albino rats were used in all experiments. The compounds (imidazole derivatives of naproxen, ketoprofen and ibuprofen) and the standard drugs were administered orally by gavage in a volume of 10 ml/kg.b.wt. Doses equivalent

of 50 mg/kg of drugs were used. The drugs were administered orally daily for 4 days. After 4 days animals were sacrificed and number of ulcer formed in gastric mucosa were examined by mean of a magnifying lens. Ulcers were counted and recorded on average number of ulcer per compound.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the management of S.B.S. (P.G.) Institute of Biomedical Sciences and Research, Balawala, Dehradum (Uttarakhand) for providing laboratory facilities.

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